

Research Article

Over four months of ethylene production: Unlocking the potential of solid-state photosynthetic cell factories

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Abstract

This study demonstrates the feasibility of solid-state photosynthetic cell factories for long-term ethylene production. Engineered *Synechocystis* sp. PCC 6803 expressing the ethylene-forming enzyme were immobilized in TEMPO-oxidized cellulose nanofiber (TCNF) matrices, using 200 μm Ca^{2+} -PVA-TCNF hydrogel films or a 2 mm Ca^{2+} -MLG-TCNF all-polysaccharide film. The solid-state thin-layer architecture supported long-term ethylene production by limiting biomass accumulation, improving light utilization and enabling more stable biocatalytic performance. Operated in a custom photobiofilm reactor under continuous-flow semi-wet cultivation, these biocatalysts sustained ethylene production for over four months, achieving up to two-fold higher yields compared with continuous-flow suspension cultures. The suspension system itself represents the first demonstration of four-month ethylene production in cyanobacteria. Biodegradation assays confirmed the environmental compatibility of TCNF matrices, with the all-polysaccharide formulation offering additional sustainability advantages. Overall, these results demonstrate the potential of solid-state

photosynthetic cell factories as a sustainable platform for photosynthetic production of solar chemicals and fuels.

Keywords

cyanobacteria, ethylene biosynthesis, nanocellulose, photosynthetic biocatalyst, photobioreactor, sustainability

Introduction

Ethylene is an indispensable material in the chemical industry, serving as a precursor for a wide range of products, from plastics to antifreeze solutions [1]. Additionally, it possesses high energy density (50.4 MJ kg^{-1}), which is comparable to that of methane (55.5 MJ kg^{-1}), making it an attractive candidate for use as a fuel [2,3]. Currently, the industrial production of ethylene relies extensively on non-renewable petroleum resources [4], making the development of sustainable and renewable production pathways critically important.

Cyanobacteria provide an attractive carbon-neutral platform for the sustainable production of ethylene and other value-added chemicals, thanks to their ability to oxidize water and fix atmospheric CO_2 through photosynthesis, using sunlight as the primary energy source. While cyanobacteria do not naturally produce ethylene, recent developments in molecular and synthetic biology have enabled their metabolic engineering and introduction of heterologous pathways for ethylene biosynthesis [5]. A significant advancement in this field has been the expression of the ethylene-forming enzyme (Efe) from *Pseudomonas syringae* in various cyanobacterial hosts, including the model organism *Synechocystis* sp. PCC 6803 [2,6]. Beyond photosynthetic systems, heterotrophic microorganisms have also been explored as production platforms. In particular, *Escherichia coli* has proven to be a versatile

host for heterologous Efe expression, demonstrating that ethylene biosynthesis can be supported in both autotrophic and heterotrophic backgrounds [7–9]. Introduction of the *e fe* gene into cyanobacteria enables the cells to reroute photosynthetically fixed CO₂ towards ethylene through 2-oxoglutarate (2-OG), an intermediate of the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle. The overall carbon transformation can be expressed by the following simplified stoichiometry:

(photosynthetic CO₂ fixation followed by metabolic conversion to 2-OG),

(conversion of 2-OG to ethylene by Efe).

It is important to note, however, that the above equations provide an oversimplified view of ethylene biosynthesis in the production host. In practice, the underlying interactions within the photoautotrophic metabolic networks are considerably more complex, as carbon flux is influenced not only by competing metabolic sinks that divert carbon away from ethylene biosynthesis [5], but also by the unusual catalytic properties of the Efe enzyme itself. Efe is an Fe(II)/2-OG-dependent oxygenase that catalyzes ethylene formation through an atypical reaction mechanism coupled to arginine-dependent side chemistry, generating additional products alongside ethylene [8,10]. As a result, the overall performance of the system depends not only on carbon partitioning toward ethylene biosynthesis, but also on how Efe catalysis interacts with host metabolism. Moreover, 2-OG is not only a key intermediate of the TCA cycle but also a central hub linking carbon and nitrogen metabolism, serving as a precursor for amino acid biosynthesis and playing a regulatory role in nitrogen assimilation [11]. Because 2-OG is shared between ethylene formation and core cellular metabolism, its

availability is shaped by both host metabolic state and Efe-associated reactions, further complicating the metabolic balance required for efficient ethylene production.

Optimization of ethylene production in engineered cyanobacteria has included the integration of codon-optimized versions of the *efe* gene under the control of various strong promoters and alternative ribosome binding site sequences [12–14]. In parallel, engineering efforts have focused on rewiring the host's central carbon metabolism to redirect carbon flux toward the TCA cycle, and more specifically, toward the formation of the Efe substrate 2-OG, including strategies that enhance carbon entry through phosphoenolpyruvate carboxylase and promote carbon partitioning toward ethylene biosynthesis [15,16]. These advances contribute to the development of cyanobacteria as photosynthetic cell factories (PCFs), a concept in which the production strain acts primarily as a biocatalyst, channeling energy and carbon directly into the synthesis of targeted chemical, while minimizing the generation of side-products [17,18]. Recent research has also shown that improving ethylene stability and yield may require attention not only to flux engineering, but also to secondary effects of Efe-associated byproducts, as guanidine formed during Efe-dependent metabolism can impose cellular stress and has been linked to genomic instability in ethylene-producing cyanobacteria [19]. However, achieving the ideal performance for ethylene-producing PCFs remains challenging, as low productivity continues to be the primary bottleneck limiting the commercial viability of ethylene production by cyanobacteria [20]. At the same time, further improvements in productivity will depend not only on strain engineering, but also on the development of cultivation platforms that support stable long-term biocatalytic performance.

In practice, PCFs are typically deployed in photobioreactors as suspension cultures. However, suspension-based production platforms utilizing PCFs still face several inherent

limitations. These include significant diversion of acquired energy and fixed carbon into biomass growth rather than product formation. Other limitations are low light utilization efficiency due to self-shading and light scattering, excessive water consumption, the need for energy-intensive operations such as mixing and contamination control during cultivation, and costly downstream processes like biomass harvesting [21,22]. Together, these challenges constrain the overall productivity and sustainability of current suspension-based production systems.

To achieve sustainable and economically viable production, fundamentally new technologies are necessary. Building upon a thin-layer immobilization approach originally developed to improve the photosynthetic production of H_2 [23–26], we recently introduced the concept of solid-state photosynthetic cell factories (solid-state PCFs). In this approach, specifically engineered photosynthetic cells are entrapped within a tailor-made, thin biobased polymeric matrix to enable sustainable and efficient production of solar chemicals and fuels [27–29]. In solid-state PCFs, both the engineered cells and the functional properties of the matrix work synergistically to enhance production. The robust matrix restricts cell division and biomass accumulation, facilitates gas diffusion, and enables efficient product separation, while the engineered metabolic pathways in the cells channel energy and carbon fluxes toward the biosynthesis of the desired product. Furthermore, solid-state configurations allow for strategic light management by minimizing self-shading through the incorporation of structural elements within the matrix, such as heterogeneous cell aggregates [30], photosynthetic antenna gradients [31,32], modified photosynthetic antennae with broadened light absorption spectra [33], and integrated optical fibers. Notably, the introduction of a photosynthetic antenna gradient alone into the architecture of H_2 -producing biocatalysts dramatically improved light utilization efficiency, enabling light-

to-H₂ conversion efficiencies exceeding 4% at peak activity and maintaining over 2% throughout a continuous 16-day production period [32].

In this research, we developed and applied ethylene-producing solid-state PCFs consisting of engineered cyanobacterial cells embedded within TEMPO-oxidized cellulose nanofiber (TCNF) matrices in a photobiofilm reactor (PhBFR). TEMPO oxidation contributes to the high optical transparency of the matrix by reducing light scattering [34,35], thereby enhancing light penetration within the film, a property particularly important for photosynthetic cells [27]. In addition, the nanofibrillar structure of TCNF provides a porous and mechanically stable scaffold that supports gas exchange and mass transfer within the biocatalyst [28,29]. To improve the productivity of gaseous ethylene, the PhBFR was designed for semi-wet cultivation of the biocatalyst, thereby enhancing ethylene separation from the immobilization matrix. Building on this system, we demonstrated the successful application of solid-state cultivation technology, achieving continuous ethylene production for over four months, the longest reported duration for cyanobacterial ethylene production to date. This extended biocatalytic performance, combined with nearly twofold higher ethylene production yields compared with conventional suspension cultures, highlights the strong potential of solid-state PCF technology as a sustainable platform for CO₂ capture and the photosynthetic production of value-added chemicals and fuels.

Results

Optimization of the long-term ethylene production by solid-state photosynthetic catalysts

To establish a stable and efficient platform for long-term ethylene production, *Synechocystis* sp. PCC 6803 pDF-lac2-S5-efe-CmR cells (hereafter *Synechocystis* efe), specifically engineered to produce ethylene *via* expression of the ethylene-forming enzyme [13], were

entrapped within Ca^{2+} -polyvinyl alcohol (PVA)-TCNF hydrogel films. The immobilization approach was implemented to restrict biomass growth and enhance the metabolic stability of ethylene-producing cells [36–38]. Together, these effects help extend photosynthetic productivity and sustain long-term functionality of the biocatalyst. The resulting *Synechocystis* efc films were placed in the PhBFR designed for semi-wet cultivation (Figure 1A), where the catalyst was maintained in a humidified atmosphere and continuously supplied with medium through the melamine foam support, alongside continuous air flows. This configuration ensured a steady delivery of nutrients and inorganic carbon while allowing efficient release and continuous monitoring of ethylene from the immobilized cells.

In the first PhBFR setup, the BG11 medium was supplemented with 200 mM NaHCO_3 (hereafter referred to as bicarbonate), and the continuous medium flow rate was varied between 5 and 30 mL h^{-1} . In this setup, we selected 200 mM bicarbonate based on previous work showing that high dissolved inorganic carbon levels support sustained ethylene production in both suspension and immobilized cultures [39]. A two-month experiment revealed that a medium flow rate of 20 mL h^{-1} , supplemented with 200 mM bicarbonate, was sufficient to sustain ethylene production (Figure 1B). However, this setup led to the pronounced bleaching of the film after approximately 55 days of cultivation, accompanied by a gradual decline in ethylene production activity over time. Increasing the medium flow rate to 30 mL h^{-1} did not mitigate this decline. Consequently, this setup yielded approximately 37.4 mmol (~ 930 mL) of ethylene per m^2 over 66 days, with an average productivity of 0.57 $\text{mmol m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$ (~ 14 $\text{mL m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$).

To further optimize the process, a second PhBFR setup was employed, where the flow rate was maintained at 20 mL h^{-1} , and bicarbonate concentration in the BG11 medium was varied from 20 to 100 mM. Under these conditions, the solid-state PCF catalyst sustained

ethylene production for over 142 days, yielding approximately 80.4 mmol (~2 L) of ethylene per m² (Figure 1C), with average productivity similar to the first PhBFR (0.57 mmol m⁻² d⁻¹). A direct comparison of daily production yields between the two PhBFR setups (Figure 1B vs Figure 1C) revealed that moderate bicarbonate loadings of 20 – 60 mM were sufficient to maintain daily ethylene production at levels achieved with 200 mM bicarbonate. As ethylene production activity began to decline after approximately 90 days of cultivation, introducing 100 mM bicarbonate at this stage failed to restore ethylene production in immobilized cells (Figure 1C).

Another key finding from these experiments was that IPTG, an inducer of *eFe* expression in *Synechocystis* cells, effectively triggered ethylene production during the early stages of the experiment. As cultivation progressed, immobilized cells no longer responded to IPTG addition (Figure 1), indicating that continued IPTG supplementation was no longer necessary to maintain the induced state.

Effect of bicarbonate loading on the long-term ethylene production by Ca²⁺-PVA-TCNF hydrogel films

Initial experiments described above revealed that moderate bicarbonate supplementation is sufficient to sustain ethylene production, suggesting that excessive bicarbonate addition may not provide further benefits. This observation contrasts with previous studies reporting that efficient ethylene production in cyanobacterial systems typically requires relatively high bicarbonate loadings to ensure sufficient inorganic carbon supply [39]. To evaluate the effect of bicarbonate concentration on solid-state PCFs, we operated three PhBFRs with Ca²⁺-PVA-TCNF films under identical medium flow rates, using BG11 medium supplemented with 20,

60, or 120 mM sodium bicarbonate. In all cases, IPTG was added only at the start of the experiment.

As shown in Figure 2A, higher bicarbonate concentrations initially enhanced ethylene production yields, consistent with earlier short-term observations [39]. However, during prolonged cultivation, high bicarbonate loadings led to a noticeably faster decline in daily production yields, accompanied by an earlier onset of visible film bleaching and reduced photochemical activity by the end of the experiment (Figure 2B). Differences between conditions became more pronounced after approximately 40 days of cultivation (Figure 2A). Consequently, total ethylene yields were 1.24, 0.72, and 0.68 L m⁻² under 20-, 60-, and 120-mM bicarbonate, respectively. To rule out genetic instability as a contributing factor, we confirmed that the decline in ethylene production was not caused by the loss or mutation of the plasmid carrying the *efe* gene in the immobilized cells under any of the tested experimental conditions (Supplementary Figure 1).

These results demonstrate that 20 mM bicarbonate is sufficient to sustain long-term biocatalytic activity, whereas higher bicarbonate concentrations reduce overall ethylene production under continuous operation. Together, these findings reveal the importance of carefully controlling bicarbonate levels in the PhBFR to maintain cell viability and productivity in solid-state PCF catalysts. Future work should evaluate lower bicarbonate concentrations, outlet carbon losses, and direct CO₂ feeding to better assess carbon utilization efficiency and improve process performance during scale-up.

Comparison of the hydrogel films with conventional suspension cultivation

To confirm the advantages of the immobilization approach over the traditional suspension-based production system, we operated the PhBFR loaded with a suspension of *Synechocystis*

efe cells. The total cell density was adjusted to match that of the immobilized films, normalized based on chlorophyll *a* (Chl *a*) content. The reactor was supplied with BG11 medium containing 20 mM bicarbonate at a flow rate of 20 mL h⁻¹. To prevent cell sedimentation, the suspension culture in the PhBFR was continuously and vigorously mixed using magnetic stirring throughout the experiment.

The suspension culture cumulatively produced 1.8-fold less ethylene than the immobilized system under the same operational conditions, yielding 26.6 mmol m⁻² (~0.66 L m⁻²) of ethylene over 129 days (Figure 3), compared to 50 mmol m⁻² (1.24 L m⁻²) produced by the Ca²⁺-PVA-TCNF hydrogel film over the same period (Figure 4). The average daily productivities were approximately 0.2 mmol m⁻² d⁻¹ for the suspension culture and 0.39 mmol m⁻² d⁻¹ for the film. A slight increase in daily productivity observed in the suspension culture after ~35 days of cultivation (Figure 3) may be associated with the formation of a surface-associated biofilm on the reactor walls.

Unlike the immobilized system, the suspension culture required periodic additions of 1 mM IPTG to maintain *efe* expression. This was necessary because continuous cell growth and medium turnover gradually diluted intracellular inducer levels. In the absence of IPTG supplementation, ethylene production declined progressively (Supplementary Figure 2). Under continuous medium flow conditions, a rapid decrease in cell density, measured as Chl *a* content, was observed in the suspension culture, declining from approximately 5.5 mg Chl *a* per PhBFR to around 1 mg Chl *a* within the first few days, and remaining at low levels (typically below ~1.2 mg Chl *a*) throughout the cultivation period (Figure 3). In contrast, immobilized cells maintained a more stable Chl *a* content under similar operating conditions (Supplementary Figure 3).

Overall, the immobilized system achieved approximately twofold higher ethylene productivity under identical operating conditions. In contrast, the suspension culture required continuous mixing and repeated IPTG supplementation, resulting in reduced long-term performance.

Bioinspired formulation for long-term ethylene production

In the final set of experiments, we selected an all-polysaccharide-based Ca^{2+} -mixed-linkage glucan (MLG)-TCNF matrix formulation as the most promising candidate for long-term application [40]. This choice was based on its excellent performance in entrapping *Synechocystis* efe cells in short-term ethylene production [41]. Unlike the previous approach based on conventional atmospheric drying [41], we adopted an osmotic dehydration technique to prepare the films, resulting in a porosity gradient across the matrix and improved structural properties [42,43].

As shown in Figure 4, the all-polysaccharide-based film outperformed the Ca^{2+} -PVA-TCNF formulation in total ethylene production yield under identical cultivation conditions, reaching approximately 58 mmol m^{-2} (1.44 L m^{-2}) over 130 days, corresponding to an average daily productivity of $\sim 11 \text{ mL m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$. However, it is important to note that the osmotic dehydration approach produced a significantly thicker film ($\sim 2 \text{ mm}$), approximately ten times thicker than the $\sim 200 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ Ca^{2+} -PVA-TCNF matrix prepared using the coating approach. When normalized to catalyst volume, this led to a markedly lower space-time yield of $0.22 \text{ mmol ethylene L}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$ for the 2 mm Ca^{2+} -MLG-TCNF film, compared to $1.9 \text{ mmol ethylene L}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$ for the $200 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ Ca^{2+} -PVA-TCNF film. Nonetheless, both immobilized systems dramatically outperformed the suspension culture in terms of space-time yield, which remained around $0.007 \text{ mmol ethylene L}_{\text{medium}}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$. These results demonstrate the clear

advantage of the solid-state PCF architecture for long-term ethylene production, combining improved productivity with reduced operational demands.

Rapid enzymatic degradation test for TCNF-based dry films and hydrogels

To evaluate the environmental sustainability and end-of-life degradability of the developed TCNF-based immobilization matrices, we subjected self-standing hydrogels and completely dried TCNF-based films to rapid laboratory-scale enzymatic degradation (Figure 5A). After 48 hours of incubation, the dry PVA-TCNF and MLG-TCNF films had completely disintegrated, while the corresponding Ca^{2+} -crosslinked hydrogels had liquefied. The reducing sugar content analysis revealed that 65 – 70% of the films' and 35 – 40% of the hydrogels' dry matter had hydrolyzed to soluble sugar oligomers (Figure 5B). The dry films degraded more than the hydrogels in 48 hours regardless of the crosslinking additive. However, the all-polysaccharide MLG-crosslinked materials degraded slightly more than the materials containing synthetic PVA.

Discussion

Establishment of long-term ethylene production in growth-limited solid-state PCFs

The long-term operation of solid-state PCFs enabled sustained ethylene production for over four months under continuous-flow conditions (Figures 1, 2 and 4), demonstrating relatively stable biocatalytic performance. Immobilization shifts microbial production from suspension cultivation, characterized by intensive biomass formation, to a catalysis-driven regime with restricted growth [36,44]. Such a shift has been reported in both immobilized phototrophic and heterotrophic systems, where limiting cell division stabilizes metabolic output and reduces carbon losses to biomass [31,44,45]. This growth-restricted state can be reinforced

further by controlled stress conditions, such as nutrient limitation or other environmental constraints that suppress biomass accumulation while preserving biocatalytic function [46,47]. A similar effect can also be achieved through targeted engineering strategies, for example by repressing essential genes to restrict cell division and redirect cellular resources toward product formation [48,49].

In the present system, however, growth restriction was not immediate or complete, despite the relatively high biomass loading within the TCNF-based hydrogel matrix. The data indicates a short (~3-day) initial phase of adaptation, characterized by a minor decline in Chl α content followed by recovery, most likely due to residual growth within the immobilized matrix (Supplementary Figure 3). This suggests that the relatively soft hydrogel matrix did not fully prevent cell division at the beginning of cultivation, but instead allowed a brief period of residual growth before transition to a more stabilized, growth-restricted state. Such initial growth becomes even more apparent at low biomass loading, as shown previously [41]. Under the most optimal conditions, this was followed by a stabilized biocatalytic phase lasting approximately 20 - 25 days, after which both Chl α content (Supplementary Figure 3) and production activity gradually declined (Figure 2). Notably, the decline in production activity could not be mitigated by increasing the medium flow rate or bicarbonate supply (Figure 1), indicating that factors beyond nutrient availability contributed to the observed loss of activity.

The shift towards a more stabilized, growth-restricted state may also help explain the reduced responsiveness to IPTG observed during prolonged cultivation (Figure 1). Although the underlying causes are not fully understood, our results suggest that the loss of inducer responsiveness is more likely linked to the physiological state of densely packed, growth-restricted cells than to limitations in IPTG diffusion, consistent with previous observations

that induction behavior changes in the immobilized state compared to suspension cultures [45]. In such physiological states, cells often show reduced responsiveness to external induction while maintaining prolonged metabolic activity, as reported for microbial biofilms and other growth-limited systems [50]. The initial responsiveness to IPTG during early cultivation confirms that the inducer was able to reach the cells effectively. However, the later loss of responsiveness cannot be explained solely by Efe abundance, since stable Efe pools and leaky basal expression may help maintain activity in growth-restricted cells, while substrate availability rather than transcription becomes limiting. The reduced responsiveness may also partly reflect properties of the expression system itself, as the $P_{A1lacO-1}$ promoter used in the *e*fe strain has been reported to exhibit leaky expression in *Synechocystis* [6,33]. Despite this limitation, the $P_{A1lacO-1}$ system was selected because it has previously served as a useful tuneable expression platform in *Synechocystis*, both in suspension and immobilized cultures [13,51,52]. According to Guerrero et al. [6], endogenous compounds such as allolactose may interfere with LacI-mediated repression in *Synechocystis*. Although this was not directly assessed in the present study, such an effect could in principle contribute to the reduced responsiveness of the expression system during prolonged cultivation. Alternative IPTG-independent strategies for *e*fe expression have also been reported in cyanobacteria, including constitutive, metal-inducible, and light-regulated promoters, as summarized by Carbonell et al. (2019) [53]. For example, P_{trc} has been used for *e*fe expression but, owing to its leakiness in this host, is generally considered constitutively active [6,12]. By contrast, metal-inducible promoters such as P_{PetE} (Cu) may provide tighter regulation, but their use can be complicated by metal-dependent metabolic side effects in cyanobacteria [54]. Thus, both the initial IPTG induction and subsequent leaky expression may have contributed to maintaining Efe activity during prolonged cultivation. In

addition to promoter leakiness and physiological adaptation, plasmid copy number may also have supported long-term expression stability, since RSF1010-based replicative plasmids have previously been reported to remain relatively stable in *Synechocystis* even in the absence of antibiotic selection under active growth conditions [55]. In that study, pDF-lac2 was present at approximately 2.4 copies per chromosome in suspension culture, which was suggested to be sufficient for stable maintenance over 42 days. However, owing to the spatial heterogeneity of the films, direct assessment of copy-number dynamics in the present system would require destructive sampling of replicate immobilized films at multiple time points over the four-month cultivation period and was therefore beyond the scope of this study. Instead, we limited our analysis to a plasmid retention test, which confirmed the presence and integrity of the plasmid carrying the *eFe* gene at the conclusion of the experiments (Supplementary Figure 1).

Overall, the entrapment of *eFe* cells in a thin-layer hydrogel matrix, despite its relatively low rigidity, appears to support long-term ethylene production by shifting the system from biomass growth toward a growth-restricted biocatalytic state that is associated with sustained ethylene-producing activity and reduced dependence on continuous induction.

Balanced bicarbonate supply is critical for stable long-term biocatalytic performance

As an essential inorganic carbon source, HCO_3^- supports CO_2 fixation and maintains a sustained carbon flux for ethylene production [15]. In line with this role, increasing bicarbonate concentration enhanced ethylene production activity during the early phase of cultivation (Figure 2), as also observed previously [39]. However, during prolonged operation, excessive supplementation can be detrimental, potentially inducing osmotic stress and disrupting the C/N balance in ethylene-producing cells [56–58]. In the present

study, this became evident from the more rapid loss of productivity and earlier deterioration of the immobilized biocatalyst observed at elevated bicarbonate concentrations (Figure 2). The role of bicarbonate therefore extends beyond simple carbon delivery and becomes tightly linked to the long-term physiological stability of the solid-state biocatalyst. This suggests that the underlying cause of performance decline is more complex than simple carbon excess.

One likely explanation involves the central metabolic role of 2-OG. While 2-OG serves as the direct substrate for ethylene production in the engineered *Synechocystis* efe strain, it also plays a broader role in cyanobacteria as a central metabolic hub linking carbon and nitrogen assimilation [11,59]. Under growth-restricted conditions imposed by cell entrapment within the matrix, nitrogen assimilation is likely reduced, which may increase intracellular 2-OG availability and thereby promote ethylene biosynthesis. At the same time, such metabolic shifts may disturb the native carbon flux toward the GS-GOGAT cycle, adding complexity to the interpretation of production dynamics in solid-state PCFs. In this context, moderate bicarbonate supplementation may help maintain a more favorable C/N balance, supporting more stable 2-OG dynamics and sustained ethylene biosynthesis over time.

Beyond physiological effects, bicarbonate loading is also likely to influence the physicochemical conditions within the immobilized matrix. Rapid bicarbonate consumption may locally increase pH and promote carbonate precipitation, which could compromise matrix integrity and generate localized carbon limitations [28]. Structural degradation of the immobilization matrix can result in cell loss, while diffusion limitations restrict gas, nutrient, and product exchange, causing localized substrate depletion, excessive O₂ accumulation, and matrix heterogeneity [60–62]. These factors likely destabilize the microenvironment within the matrix, impair cellular activity and accelerate the decline in ethylene production. The

presence of matrix heterogeneity is evident in the photographs taken at the end of the ethylene production experiment, where uneven film bleaching and discoloration reflect variations in biocatalyst condition (Figure 2B).

These results suggest that stable long-term performance in solid-state PCFs depends not on maximizing C_i supply, but on maintaining a balanced metabolic and physicochemical environment within the immobilized biocatalyst. Optimizing both bicarbonate levels and the structural properties of the matrix therefore appears essential for sustaining high biocatalytic efficiency in PhBFRs. Further engineering efforts should focus on improving matrix porosity and mass transfer in order to maintain a more stable and spatially uniform biocatalytic environment during prolonged operation.

Solid-state architecture outperforms suspension cultivation during long-term ethylene production

Comparing solid-state PCFs with suspension cultivation was essential to determine whether the improved long-term performance arises from the immobilized architecture itself rather than from the production strain or reactor configuration. When both systems operate in the same PhBFR under identical light, medium flow, bicarbonate supply, and initial biomass loading conditions, this comparison provides a direct assessment of how solid-state PCF format influences long-term ethylene production.

As shown in Figure 4, suspension culture exhibited lower performance than all immobilized formulations tested in this study. This advantage was also reflected in the estimated light-to-ethylene conversion efficiency (LECE) under the long-term operating conditions used here, which was in the range of 0.07 - 0.08% for the solid-state PCFs and 0.038% for the suspension culture, corresponding to ~2-fold improvement in light utilization

efficiency by the solid-state architecture over 130 days of operation. Although the absolute values are lower than the 0.3% reported previously for cyanobacterial films placed under similar light conditions [39], this value was obtained in the small, closed vials under a shorter production regime (8 days), and therefore is not directly comparable to the long-term continuous flow operation. The better long-term performance of solid-state PCFs is consistent with previous reports showing that immobilized cyanobacterial systems can maintain higher or more sustained productivities than free-cell cultures, particularly during prolonged or repeated operation [26,51,63,64]. This may reflect differences in carbon partitioning, with suspension cultures directing a larger fraction of energy and fixed carbon toward biomass accumulation rather than product synthesis, potentially reducing the availability of 2-oxoglutarate for ethylene biosynthesis [2,5,16]. In our system, suspension cultures were further affected by cell washout under continuous medium flow. The applied medium flow rate (20 mL h^{-1}) corresponds to a dilution rate of approximately 0.04 h^{-1} , which falls within the range reported for continuous cultivation of wild-type *Synechocystis* PCC 6803 [65], but may still have been too high for stable biomass maintenance in the ethylene-producing strain under the applied conditions. Previous studies have indeed shown that growth of efe-expressing strains is highly sensitive to cultivation conditions [66]. In addition to cell washout, a physiological contribution to the observed decline in suspension performance cannot be excluded. The shift to continuous-flow, well-mixed production conditions may have altered the light environment, nutrient exposure, and overall metabolic state of the cells, while repeated IPTG inductions may also have imposed additional stress on the culture. Consistent with this idea, a slight decline in Chl a content was also observed in the films during the first day of cultivation (Supplementary Figure 3), suggesting that the transition to production conditions itself imposed an initial stress on the cells. In the

immobilized system, however, this initial decline was followed by recovery and transition to a more stabilized, growth-restricted state, whereas the suspension culture continued to lose biomass. As a result, the suspension culture maintained a low cell density for most of the cultivation period (Figure 3), which likely reduced self-shading but also limited the number of active cells available for ethylene production. By contrast, immobilization enhanced cell retention and thereby supported higher ethylene yields and more sustained long-term productivity (Figure 4). Using the time-weighted average Chl *a* content during cultivation and an empirical Chl-to-dry biomass conversion for the efe strain, the average suspension-culture productivity in the present PhBFR experiment for the whole cultivation period was estimated at approximately 0.042 mmol ethylene gDW⁻¹ h⁻¹. This value falls within the range (0.026–0.112 mmol ethylene gDW⁻¹ h⁻¹) of previously reported cyanobacterial ethylene productivities summarized by Eckert et al. [8], although it is lower than the highest values obtained under more optimized short-term conditions. Nevertheless, it remains comparable in magnitude, especially given the low light intensity, continuous-flow operation, biomass washout, and loss of ethylene in the medium under the long-term conditions used in this study.

Additionally, suspension cultivation required constant mixing to prevent sedimentation and repeated IPTG additions to maintain production, increasing the maintenance demands of the system during long-term operation. In contrast, the immobilized films functioned with lower intervention while sustaining better long-term performance. These observations further highlight the advantages of solid-state PCFs not only in terms of productivity, but also from an operational and economic perspective. Taken together, the comparison shows that the advantage of immobilization arises from a combination of improved biomass retention, reduced washout under continuous flow, and lower operational demands.

Bioinspired all-polysaccharide matrix design as a route toward more sustainable photosynthetic production

To further improve the sustainability of solid-state PCFs, we explored an all-polysaccharide matrix in which MLG served as a bio-based crosslinker for the TCNF network, providing an alternative to the PVA-containing formulation [41]. This bioinspired design was motivated by the natural role of hemicelluloses in plant cell walls, where they contribute to mechanical integrity, hydration, and transport properties [40]. This matrix design was combined with osmotic dehydration as the film fabrication approach [42]. This method enabled the formation of a porosity gradient across the matrix volume, resulting in more uniform dehydration and enhanced mass transport properties compared with standard drying methods [43]. In addition, the MLG-TCNF formulation produced films with excellent mechanical stability [41], a critical factor for maintaining structural integrity and function during extended cultivation. Together, these features make the approach particularly attractive for long-term photosynthetic production, where both efficient internal transport and sustained matrix stability are essential for maintaining biocatalyst performance.

The MLG-TCNF biocatalyst showed the highest cumulative ethylene yield among the tested films (Figure 4). However, in the present implementation, osmotic dehydration produced a 10-time thicker film, and its volumetric productivity was therefore lower than that of the thinner PVA-TCNF film, most likely due to stronger self-shading and internal light limitation within the matrix. Importantly, this effect should not be interpreted as a limitation of osmotic dehydration itself, since the method could likely be further optimized to produce thinner films. Instead, the present results suggest that the current architecture could be further refined to achieve a better balance between cell loading and light penetration.

Overall, these results suggest that higher productivity will require biocatalysts that maintain high cell density and sufficient thickness for high catalyst loading, while achieving more efficient internal light distribution to minimize self-shading. To improve light delivery within the matrix, more advanced architectural designs of the biocatalyst could be explored, including cell clustering [30], gradual truncation of photosynthetic antennae to reduce ineffective light absorption [32], incorporation of novel materials that enhance light distribution throughout the film, or a combination of these approaches. Such strategies could help achieve a better balance between light availability, cell density, and overall productivity in future immobilized systems.

Biodegradation assessment for the cell immobilization matrices

Controlled degradation of the cellulose-based immobilization matrices links the solid-state PCFs to circular bioeconomy at end-of-life and provides a sustainable conclusion to months of continuous ethylene production. Both the TCNF-based hydrogels and completely dried films started disintegrating in less than 48 hours after addition of cellulose- and hemicellulose-degrading enzymes, demonstrating rapid on-demand biodegradability (Figure 5).

Differences were observed between the degradation of dry films and hydrogels, and PVA- or MLG-crosslinked materials. The more extensive degradation of dry films in comparison to hydrogels is likely explained by improved enzyme accessibility to thin and dry structures, whereas the bulkier hydrogels likely restricted enzymatic hydrolysis due to a combination of slow diffusion and a lower effective substrate concentration. Nevertheless, given more time, the TCNF-based hydrogels would likely degrade as thoroughly as the dry films. Previous studies have indeed demonstrated excellent enzymatic degradation of TCNF [67], as well as

extensive microbial mineralization under both aerobic and anaerobic conditions [68]. In the latter case, TCNF exhibited near-complete biodegradation comparable to that of native cellulose nanofibers, although at a reduced rate. This decrease in degradation rate has been shown to correlate well with the increasing degree of substitution in the cellulose derivatives, which can hinder microbial or enzymatic access to the cellulose backbone [69]. Despite such variations in degradation kinetics, all native and chemically modified cellulose-based films that exhibited partial degradation in 48-hour enzymatic tests were found to fully disintegrate in prolonged, pilot-scale composting experiments [69].

Taken together, our enzymatic degradation experiments confirm the high biodegradability of TCNF-based cell immobilization matrices. However, it is important to note that the degradation of PVA-containing materials could potentially contribute to microplastic formation [70]. This further emphasizes the importance of advancing all-polysaccharide immobilization matrices with MLG or other bio-based crosslinkers that offer a fully biodegradable and environmentally safer alternative to PVA-based materials for long-term applications such as continuous ethylene production.

Concluding remarks

This study demonstrates the strong potential of solid-state PCFs as a platform for long-term light-driven ethylene production using cyanobacterial cells entrapped within thin nanocellulose-based matrices. Specifically, the engineered *Synechocystis* efe cells were introduced within Ca²⁺-PVA-TCNF and Ca²⁺-MLG-TCNF formulations, forming stable biocatalysts that sustained ethylene biosynthesis under ambient conditions for up to four months without reinduction or catalyst replacement. This contrasts sharply with state-of-the-art electrochemical CO₂-to-ethylene devices, which typically degrade within 14 to 200 h

due to catalyst deactivation or electrolyte breakdown [71,72], whereas direct hydrogenation of CO₂ requires high-temperature and high-pressure conditions [73,74].

Under identical operating conditions, solid-state PCFs clearly outperformed the suspension cultures in productivity, demonstrating the advantage of biocatalytic architecture for sustained photosynthetic production under the tested conditions. At the same time, the suspension system itself represented the first demonstration of long-term ethylene production under continuous-flow conditions. Process optimization further showed that moderate bicarbonate concentrations (20–60 mM) were sufficient to support prolonged ethylene production, whereas higher bicarbonate loadings became detrimental during extended operation.

The results also show that matrix composition and biocatalyst architecture are important determinants of biocatalytic performance. In particular, the all-polysaccharide MLG-TCNF formulation provides a promising route toward more sustainable biocatalyst architectures, while the observed differences in volumetric productivity emphasize the need for further optimization of light distribution within high cell density films. Together with the demonstrated biodegradability of the TCNF-based matrices, these findings position solid-state PCFs as a robust and environmentally promising platform for long-term photosynthetic production.

STAR★METHODS

METHODS DETAILS

Culture growth

The ethylene-producing non-motile *Synechocystis* sp. PCC 6803 strain pDF-lac2-S5-efe-CmR (*Synechocystis* efe) was used in the experiments [13]. The cells were maintained in BG11 medium containing 20 mM HEPES-NaOH (pH 7.5) at 30°C, supplemented with 25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ spectinomycin and 10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ chloramphenicol. The culture flasks were placed in a versatile environmental chamber (MLR-351, Sanyo, Japan) under continuous shaking (120 rpm) on a rotary shaker in an atmosphere containing 1% CO₂. Illumination was provided by continuous fluorescent light (Philips Master TL-D 36W/865) at approximately 35 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ of photosynthetically active radiation (PAR).

Experimental cultures were grown without antibiotics and without agitation in 1 L flat round-neck Roux-type flasks (DURAN®, Schott, DWK Life Sciences GmbH) containing ~800 mL of BG11 medium. These cultures were continuously bubbled with sterile filtered air supplemented with 1% CO₂ (0.2 μm , Acro 37 TF, Gelman Sciences). Cells were harvested at OD₇₅₀ of around 1 – 1.5 by centrifugation at 5000 g for 10 min (Avanti JXN-26, JA10, Beckman Coulter).

Materials for cell immobilization

A water suspension of TEMPO-oxidized cellulose nanofibers (TCNF) with a final consistency of approximately 1 wt% was prepared as described previously [27,29]. Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) (Mowiol® 56-98, $M_w \sim 195 \text{ kg mol}^{-1}$, DP 4300; Sigma-Aldrich) was dissolved in Milli-Q water at 90 °C in a water bath to prepare a 5 wt% solution. Low-viscosity barley mixed-linkage glucan (MLG) ($M_w \sim 179 \text{ kg mol}^{-1}$; Megazyme, catalog number P-BGBL) was used to prepare a 1 wt% solution in Milli-Q water, as described previously [41]. A poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) solution (20 wt%) was prepared by dissolving solid PEG ($M_n 35 \text{ kg mol}^{-1}$) in Milli-

Q water. All solutions and matrix formulations used for cell immobilization were sterilized by autoclaving.

Fabrication of Ca²⁺-PVA-TCNF hydrogel films

For the preparation of Ca²⁺-PVA-TCNF hydrogel films, the collected *Synechocystis* efe pellet was resuspended in Milli-Q water at a ratio of 1 g (wet biomass) to 1 mL (Milli-Q water). The resulting suspension was then thoroughly mixed at a 1 : 1 ratio with a hydrogel formulation consisting of 1 wt% TCNF and 0.1 wt% PVA using a digital Ultra-Turrax homogenizer (IKA, Staufen, Germany) at 12000 rpm for 1 min. After mixing, air bubbles were removed by centrifugation at 3000 g for 5 min, and the final formulation was coated onto the surface of the Watman paper support using an automatic film applicator (TQC Sheen) and 200 µm-graded Mayer rods. The hydrogel matrix atop the paper was then stabilized by spraying 50 mM CaCl₂ over the surface, resulting in a stable 7.5 cm x 15.5 cm (116.25 cm²) Ca²⁺-PVA-TCNF hydrogel film.

The fabricated film was placed in a 1 L PhBFR on a water-conveying melamine foam support (Figure 1A) and allowed to adapt for one day in a closed PhBFR filled with 486 mL BG11 medium under an air atmosphere before the ethylene production phase. The PhBFR with the film was continuously illuminated from the top by fluorescence lamps (Philips Master TL-D 36W/865), providing approximately 40 µmol photons m⁻² s⁻¹ PAR.

Fabrication of all-polysaccharide-based Ca²⁺-MLG-TCNF hydrogel film via osmotic dehydration

Bioinspired all-polysaccharide-based Ca²⁺-MLG-TCNF film with entrapped ethylene-producing *Synechocystis* efe cells was prepared using osmotic dehydration in a specialized casting frame, following the procedure described by Guccini et al. [43] with modifications for the upscaled fabrication of rectangular (7.5 cm × 15 cm) films.

The film formulation was prepared by mixing 1 wt% TCNF and 0.1 wt% MLG with *Synechocystis* cell suspension ($OD_{750} = 1$ in Milli-Q water) at a 1:1 ratio using a digital Ultra-Turrax homogenizer. Air bubbles were removed by centrifugation at 3000 g for 5 min. The casting frame was 3D-printed using PLA and designed to hold a dialysis membrane (6–8 kDa cut-off), which was affixed to the bottom of the frame using super glue, forming an internal chamber for filling with 200 mL of the MLG-TCNF-cell formulation. The frame was placed into a second container with 200 mL of 20% PEG, ensuring full contact between the dialysis membrane and the PEG surface without air bubbles. The PEG solution in the second container was stirred with a magnetic bar on a stirring plate, and osmotic dehydration was carried out for 4 days. Following dehydration, the produced film was treated with 50 mM $CaCl_2$, washed in Milli-Q water, and used directly for ethylene production without any further adaptation.

Long-term ethylene production by immobilised and suspension cultures

The long-term ethylene production experiments were performed in a custom-built PhBFR with a total internal volume of 1 L, consisting of a main glass chamber with an attached bottom ledge and a separate glass cover plate (Figure 1A). The bottom ledge of the chamber was sealed onto the glass plate using a ~1 mm silicone gasket coated on both sides with vacuum grease to ensure tight sealing, and the assembly was secured with binder clips. The PhBFR was equipped with inlet and outlet ports for continuous delivery of BG11 medium and air. Medium and air entered the reactor on one side and exited on the opposite side, maintaining unidirectional flow across the chamber. The working liquid volume inside the PhBFR was defined by the height of the outlet port and was approximately 486 mL.

For semi-wet cultivation, the fabricated film was placed on a water-conveying melamine foam support, which was partially submerged in BG11 medium. This ensured that the film surface remained a few millimetres above the liquid, allowing the entire catalyst to remain exposed to the gas phase while receiving moisture and nutrients through capillary transport from the foam. The PhBFR was operated under fully sterile conditions and continuously illuminated from the top by fluorescence lamps (Philips Master TL-D 36W/865), providing about $40 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ PAR. Continuous medium flow was supplied by a digital peristaltic pump (#07525-20, MasterFlex) at a rate defined by the specific experimental setup, while the air flow rate of 10 mL min^{-1} was controlled by the high precision digital mass flow controller (Red-y Smart series, Vögtlin Instruments). The synthetic air (containing 21% O_2 in N_2 , Woikoski Oy) was sterilized by passing through $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ filters (Acro 37 TF, Gelman Sciences). NaHCO_3 was introduced into the BG11 medium at different concentrations depending on the experimental setup and served as the carbon source. Bicarbonate was used instead of gaseous CO_2 because it provides a highly soluble and stable carbon source. Delivering an equivalent carbon load *via* CO_2 would require high gas-transfer rates, potentially diluting ethylene and causing medium acidification. Ethylene production was initiated by the introduction of 1 mM IPTG in the PhBFR medium.

The experiment with suspension cultures was conducted in a similar PhBFR setup, with continuous mixing provided by a magnetic stirrer to prevent cell sedimentation and ensure homogeneity. The initial Chl *a* concentration in the 500 mL suspension was adjusted to match the average total Chl *a* content in the fabricated films. The experimental conditions (i.e., medium and gas flow rates, bicarbonate concentration, temperature, and illumination) were identical for both setups, allowing a direct comparison of ethylene production between immobilized and suspension cultures.

The ethylene content in the PhBFR setup was monitored in the discharged gas flow using gas chromatography (GC, Clarus 580, PerkinElmer, Inc.). GC was equipped with Carboxen 1010 PLOT 30 m × 0.53 mm capillary column and a flame ionization detector set at 150°C with H₂ and airflow fixed at 30 mL min⁻¹ and 300 mL min⁻¹, respectively. Argon (99.99%, Woikoski Oy) was used as a carrier gas at a flow rate of ~9.8 mL min⁻¹ (18 psi). The ethylene content was determined from 40 µL gas samples collected using a gastight sample lock syringe (1705SL, Hamilton) several times per day. The average daily production yields were then calculated based on the air flow rate through the PhBFR and a calibration curve. The concentration of ethylene dissolved in the liquid phase was not considered due to its negligibly low solubility relative to its content in the gas phase. To express the production of ethylene in volumetric units, the amount of ethylene (mol) was converted to liters using the ideal gas law under the experimental conditions of 30°C and 1 atm (1 mol ≈ 24.87 L). The light-to-ethylene conversion efficiencies (LECEs) were estimated from the cumulative ethylene yields over 130 days of PhBFR operation as the ratio of the chemical energy stored in ethylene, calculated from its standard higher heating value, to the total incident light energy at 9 W m⁻² (40 µmol photons m⁻² s⁻¹ PAR), as previously described [39]. For the immobilized systems, catalyst volume used for calculating space-time yield was estimated from the film area and average film thickness. For the suspension culture, the working liquid volume of the PhBFR was used as the reference volume.

Due to the long duration of each run (several weeks to months), experimental conditions were performed once or, in some cases, twice. Although no statistical hypothesis testing was applied, the sequential design of the study allowed later experiments to confirm and reinforce observations from previous runs. Variability between runs was evaluated qualitatively based on production trends and reactor performance metrics.

Photosynthetic activity

The effective quantum yield of photosystem II [$Y(II)$] was measured using a PAM 2000 fluorometer (Walz, Germany) at several randomly selected spots across each film, both immediately after immobilization and at the end of the experiment. Prior to measurement, the film was dark-adapted for 10 minutes. A saturating light pulse ($3000 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ for 0.6 s) was applied on top of actinic light at $40 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ to determine $Y(II)$ at each spot.

Chlorophyll determination

The Chl a concentration in film samples or cell pellets was determined spectrophotometrically from the absorbance difference at 665 and 720 nm after overnight dark extraction of the collected material in 90% methanol at 4°C, using the extinction coefficient reported by Lichtenthaler [75]. The initial Chl a content in the films was determined from three 1 cm² samples collected from the edge of the film immediately after immobilization. Except for the suspension experiments, Chl a content was not monitored routinely during the long-term PhBFR runs, because repeated determination would have required destructive sampling of the immobilized films and periodic opening of the reactor. In the suspension experiments, samples for Chl a determination were collected from the outlet medium flow. Bleaching of the films was followed visually during cultivation as a progressive change in film color. Changes in Chl a content were assessed in a separate 60-day experiment under 20 mM bicarbonate supplementation by collecting three 1 cm² samples from the films at each sampling time point (Supplementary Figure 3).

Sample preparation for enzymatic degradation

Dry TCNF films were prepared using the solvent-casting method, incorporating either PVA or MLG crosslinking additives, both of which have been shown to strengthen the TCNF network

by bridging nanofibrils [40,76]. PVA and MLG were added to their individual 0.5 wt% TCNF suspensions in amounts corresponding to 10% and 5% of the cellulose dry weight, respectively. The mixtures were homogenized using a high-performance dispersing instrument (Ultra-Turrax, IKA-Werke) at 13000 rpm for 2 min and degassed with a vacuum-assisted asymmetric centrifuge (SpeedMixer DAC 600, Synergy Devices Ltd.) operated at 1600 rpm and 100 mbar. Finally, the mixtures were cast into 8 cm Petri dishes and dried at 50% RH and 23°C for 4 days. The dried films were cut into approximately 1 cm x 1 cm pieces. The mean thicknesses of the dry PVA-TCNF and MLG-TCNF films were 22 μm and 26 μm , respectively.

Self-standing \sim 1 wt% TCNF hydrogels, incorporating the same PVA and MLG additives as the dry films, were prepared following previously described methods [29,41]. The materials were initially mixed at 0.5 wt% TCNF consistency, then cast onto a solid support and Ca^{2+} -crosslinked to produce self-standing, low-solid-content hydrogels. After casting, the hydrogels were partially dewatered, then re-wetted by immersion in 25 ml of Milli-Q water and stored for 7 days at 4°C. Before enzymatic degradation, the hydrogels were cut into approximately 1 cm x 1 cm pieces. The Ca^{2+} -PVA-TCNF and Ca^{2+} -MLG-TCNF hydrogels had approximate thicknesses of 1 mm.

Enzymatic degradation

The biodegradation assessment for the TCNF-based films and hydrogels was carried out with enzymatic degradation, following the method described by Leppänen et al. [69]. The enzyme mix was prepared according to Tenkanen et al. [77] using commercially available enzymes: Gamanase, Novozyme 188 (Novozymes, Denmark), Econase and Ecopulp X-200 (AB Enzymes, Finland). The enzyme mix contained cellulase, mannanase, xylanase and β -

glucosidase activities with a measured overall activity of 20 FPU/ml (filter paper unit/ml).

The required volume of the enzyme mix was calculated according to Equation 1,

$$\text{Volume of the enzyme mix} = \frac{50 \left(\frac{\text{FPU}}{\text{g}} \right) \times \text{Dry weight of the sample (g)}}{\text{Activity of the enzyme mix} \left(\frac{\text{FPU}}{\text{ml}} \right)} \quad (1)$$

where a target enzyme activity of 50 FPU per gram of sample dry mass was used for the degradation. The experiments were conducted in 10 ml glass vials, where ~1 cm² film and hydrogel pieces with known dry matter contents were weighed. Then, sodium acetate buffer (0.5 M, pH 5) and MQ water were added to obtain a 0.7 wt% sample dry weight and 50 mM total ionic strength. Enzymatic degradation was initiated by adding the enzyme mix to the vials, which were then incubated at 40°C for 48 h with constant shaking. A reference sample containing only the enzyme mix was also prepared to account for background effects. After the incubation period, the samples were centrifuged at 3200 rpm for 10 min. The resulting supernatant, which contained the hydrolyzed sugar oligomers and enzymes, was boiled for 10 min to inactivate the enzymes. The precipitated enzymes were then separated by centrifugation and discarded. The reducing sugar content in the remaining supernatant was analysed using a dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) reagent (1% DNS, 1.6% NaOH, and 30% potassium sodium tartrate), following the method described by Sumner and Noback [78]. The degree of enzymatic hydrolysis for the samples was calculated with Equation 2,

$$\text{Degree of hydrolysis (\%)} = \frac{\text{Reducing sugar content (g/l)}}{\text{Dry weight of the sample (g/l)}} \quad (2)$$

where the reducing sugar content in the supernatant was compared to the initial dry weight of the sample.

RESOURCE AVAILABILITY

Lead contact

Further information and requests for resources and materials should be directed to, and will be handled by, the lead contact, Sergey Kosourov (serkos@utu.fi).

Materials availability

This study did not generate new proprietary materials. The solid-state PCFs were fabricated using established protocols and commercially available chemicals, as described in the Experimental Details section.

Data and code availability

All data supporting the findings of this study are available within the main text or the Supplemental Information. This paper does not report original code. Additional information required to reanalyze the data is available from the lead contact upon request.

Author contributions

Conceptualization and methodology – S.K., Y.A.; investigation of long-term ethylene production – S.K., V.S., G.T., P.K., Y.A.; investigation of biodegradation – T.L., T.T.; data analysis – S.K., T.L., G.T., V.S.; resources – Y.A., P.K., T.T.; funding acquisition – Y.A., T.T.; writing (original draft on long-term ethylene production) – S.K.; writing (original draft on biodegradation) – T.L.; writing (review & editing) – all authors.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Technology readiness

From a technology-readiness perspective, the present work corresponds approximately to TRL 4. The study advances beyond initial proof-of-concept by demonstrating sustained operation of solid-state photosynthetic cell factories in a dedicated continuous-flow laboratory reactor and by showing stable ethylene production for over four months under controlled conditions. Through long-term experiments with immobilized cyanobacterial biocatalysts, together with direct comparison to suspension cultures under identical operating conditions, we demonstrated that the solid-state

architecture can support prolonged functionality and improved long-term productivity. However, further optimization of productivity, carbon utilization, matrix performance, and reactor integration will be required before validation in a more application-relevant environment. Key challenges, including carbon efficiency, durability of the immobilized biocatalyst, reactor scale-up, and cost-effective operation, must be addressed before pilot-scale testing of this technology.

Highlights

Solid-state photosynthetic cell factories enabled continuous ethylene production by cyanobacteria for over four months.

Thin-layer photosynthetic biocatalysts outperformed suspension cultures under identical continuous-flow operating conditions.

Long-term ethylene production was maintained without antibiotic selection, while in solid-state photosynthetic cell factories, additional IPTG was not required after initial induction.

Moderate bicarbonate supply supported the most stable long-term ethylene production in the photobiofilm reactor.

All-polysaccharide TCNF-based matrices provided a durable and more sustainable platform for photosynthetic bioproduction.

Figure legends

Figure 1. Continuous ethylene production by solid-state photosynthetic cell factories in the PhBFR system. (A) Schematic representation of the PhBFR setup for long-term ethylene production using solid-state photosynthetic cell factories: (1) BG11 medium reservoir; (2) digital peristaltic pump; (3) compressed air cylinder; (4) digital mass flow controller; (5) PhBFR containing the photosynthetic thin-layer biocatalyst, with a close-up showing the photosynthetic catalyst positioned on the melamine foam support; (6) light panel; (7) vessel for collecting discharged medium; (8) gas-tight syringe for gas sampling; (9) photosynthetic biocatalyst; (10) foam support; (11) medium. (B) Ethylene production by Ca^{2+} -PVA-TCNF hydrogel film with entrapped *Synechocystis* efe cells under varying BG11 medium flow rates with 200 mM sodium bicarbonate. (C) Ethylene production by the film under a fixed BG11 flow rate of 20 mL h^{-1} , where bicarbonate concentration in the medium was adjusted several times between 20 – 100 mM during the experiment. In all experiments, the air flow rate was maintained at 10 mL min^{-1} . Additions of 1 mM IPTG are indicated by arrows (introduced directly into the PhBFR) and bracketed arrows (introduced into the BG11 medium reservoir). The time point at which bleaching of the film first became visually apparent is indicated by a blue arrow.

Figure 2. Effect of bicarbonate concentration on long-term ethylene production and hydrogel film stability. (A) Daily ethylene production yield over time under continuous BG11 medium flow (20 mL h^{-1}) and constant air supply (10 mL min^{-1}) for Ca^{2+} -PVA-TCNF hydrogel films loaded with 20 mM (cyan), 60 mM (blue), and 120 mM (red) sodium bicarbonate. Arrows indicate the onset of visible film bleaching. (B) Visual appearance and photochemical activity of the films at the beginning (0 days) and at the end of the experiment (129, 56, and 43 days for the 20-, 60-, and 120-mM bicarbonate concentrations, respectively). $Y(\text{II})$ values represent the effective quantum yield of photosystem II, measured at several randomly

selected spots across each film; the range indicates the minimum and maximum observed values.

Figure 3. Daily ethylene production and chlorophyll *a* changes during long-term cultivation of *Synechocystis* sp. suspension culture. The PhBFR containing suspension culture was operated under continuous BG11 medium flow (20 mL h⁻¹) supplemented with 20 mM sodium bicarbonate and a constant air supply (10 mL min⁻¹). Additions of 1 mM IPTG to the PhBFR are indicated by arrows.

Figure 4. Cumulative ethylene yields from suspension culture and two photosynthetic film biocatalysts under identical operating conditions. Two hydrogel film formulations were evaluated: Ca²⁺-PVA-TCNF and Ca²⁺-MLG-TCNF. In all cases, the PhBFR was operated under continuous BG11 medium flow (20 mL h⁻¹) supplemented with 20 mM sodium bicarbonate and a constant air supply (10 mL min⁻¹). For both biocatalysts, 1 mM IPTG was added only at the beginning of the experiment; IPTG additions for the suspension culture followed the schedule described in Figure 3. Because of the long duration of the cultivation runs, the experiments were performed once, and error bars are therefore not shown.

Figure 5. Enzymatic degradation of TCNF-based dry films and hydrogels. (A) Photographs of the TCNF-based dry films and hydrogels prior to enzymatic degradation experiments. (B) The percentage of dry matter hydrolyzed to sugars after 48 h enzymatic degradation. Samples were prepared with the crosslinking additives PVA (blue), MLG (green) and Ca²⁺-ions (only in hydrogels). Enzymatic degradation was conducted in duplicate for each sample type, and degree of hydrolysis was determined twice for each duplicate.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

